

Trends in Food Science & Technology

Ensuring societal considerations are met when translating science into policy for sustainable food system transformation

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Background A food system transformation is needed to address food and nutrition security, minimise impacts on planetary health, reduce climate change emissions, and contribute to equity, diversity, and all other Sustainable Development Goals.</p> <p>Scope and Approach This paper summarizes findings of the European Commission's High Level Expert Group on Food Systems Science, which reviewed obstacles that prevent food systems policy from achieving society-wide impacts. These include knowledge and translation gaps in food-related science-policy-interfaces (SPIs), insufficient attention to the priorities of diverse stakeholders, and insufficient consideration of equity, diversity, political economy, and societal engagements.</p>

	<p>Key Findings & Conclusions Three potential pathways are proposed to ensure that science and policy support food systems transformation: (1) Adapt the current SPI landscape with extra resources and a wider mandate that reaches across the full food system, (2) Enhance the current policy landscape with a range of multisectoral taskforces, and (3) Establish a “network of networks” to provide both global coordination as well as organize defined agendas. In embarking on these pathways, a revised science-policy-society landscape (SPSIs) should deliver the following core functions: (1) Engage and empower multi-stakeholder dialogue; (2) Build capacity at multiple scales to translate evidence into real-world outcomes; (3) Ensure access to openly accessible data for the entire food system; (4) Use models, forecasts, and scenario building exercises to explore the future of food systems; (5) Produce assessment reports and policy publications; and (6) Establish fora for diplomacy, standards / target-setting and policy making.</p>
<p>Suggested Reviewers:</p>	<p>Sylvain Charlebois Dalhousie University sylvain.charlebois@dal.ca Food policy expert in Canada</p> <hr/> <p>Maria Manez Helmholtz Centre Hereon Maria.Manez@hereon.de Works on food policy in EU</p> <hr/> <p>Andy Dougill University of York andy.dougill@york.ac.uk Strong international perspective on food systems policy</p> <hr/> <p>Maggie Gill University of Aberdeen m.gill@abdn.ac.uk Former chair of science council of CGIAR</p>
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	<p>Dear Editors of Trends in Food Science and Technology,</p> <p>Thank you for the opportunity to revise and resubmit our short paper (Manuscript Number: TIFS-D-22-01592). We very much appreciate the time and support of the editorial team and both peer-reviewers. Here we reflect on how we have addressed the reviewers’ critiques and suggestions.</p> <p>Reviewer 1. Reviewer #1: The article is well written though sound like short communication or technical paper. o RESPONSE: Thank you for your time and encouragement. Reviewer #1: The authors have need to make some of the claims evidence-based through proper citation. o RESPONSE: We have edited the entire manuscript adding several references to make it clear where the evidence for our claims comes from. Reviewer #1: proper title to the figure while putting the explanation as a footnote and the source in proper order. o RESPONSE: We have changed the figure title. Reviewer #1: There is also the need to list all the names of the authors and put the year of publication in each of the reference. o RESPONSE: We have amended the reference list accordingly.</p> <p>Reviewer 2. Reviewer #2: The manuscript is a very useful summary of the HLEG report on the Science policy interfaces for sustainable food system transformation. The publication in TIFS ensures a wider uptake and understanding of the obstacles for food system transformation among food industry stakeholders who are the target readers of TIFS journal. The discussion of the potential obstacles and suggested pathways for food system transformation including wide collaboration and</p>

empowering of current networks and initiatives gives a good overview for the reader.

o RESPONSE: Thank you for your time and encouragement.

Reviewer #2: On P.5 Note the link for the full 70-page report, which this article draws on is not valid: However, the report is accessible through the reference Webb et al.

o RESPONSE: We have replaced the URL with the reference to Webb et al., 2022.

Reviewer #2: You may consider to implement a style for the headings as numbering format e.g. MAIN TEXT change to 1. Introduction etc.

o RESPONSE: We have done this.

Response to Reviewers

Reviewer #2: Since this is the background of the work and justification for publishing a summary, I suggest to add an explanation on the structure of the paper e.g. the main sections of the paper to give the reader a quick overview on the content and the key message this paper delivers beyond the HLEG report.

o RESPONSE: we have added a footnote to this effect.

We hope these changes are sufficient and address the comments made by the two reviewers. We are, of course, happy to work on future changes to improve our submission.

With many thanks,

Evan Fraser, Braj Singh, and Patrick Webb (on behalf of all the co-authors)

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Highlights

This paper reports on the findings of the European Commission's High Level Expert Group on Food Systems Science that reviewed obstacles for developing science policy interfaces for food systems.

Reviewing current initiatives revealed that science policy interfaces for food should deliver at least the following functions.

- (1) Engage and empower multi-stakeholder dialogue;
- (2) Build capacity at national and local levels to translate evidence into impact;
- (3) Ensure open access to data from across the food system;
- (4) Explore the future of food systems through modelling, forecasting, and scenarios;
- (5) Deliver independent assessment reports and policy pathway documents; and
- (6) Create a forum for diplomacy, standards and target-setting and policy making.

Developing an empowered landscape of science-policy-society-interfaces that deliver on these six functions must also be based on principles of transparency, democracy, diversity, cut across scales and sectors, and adopt a food systems transformation lens.

1 **Ensuring societal considerations are met when translating science into policy for**
 2 **sustainable food system transformation**

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ABSTRACT

Background

A food system transformation is needed to address food and nutrition security, minimise impacts on planetary health, reduce climate change emissions, and contribute to equity, diversity, and the Sustainable Development Goals.

Scope and Approach

This paper summarizes findings of the European Commission’s High Level Expert Group on Food Systems Science, which reviewed obstacles that prevent food systems policy from achieving society-wide impacts. These barriers include knowledge and translation gaps in food-related science-policy-interfaces (SPIs), insufficient attention to the priorities of diverse stakeholders, and a failure to adequately consider equity, diversity, political economy, and societal engagements.

Key Findings & Conclusions

Three potential pathways can ensure science and policy support food systems transformation: (1) *Adapt* the current SPI landscape with extra resources and a wider mandate to ensure coordinated action across the full food system, (2) *Enhance* the current policy landscape with a range of multisectoral taskforces designed to fulfill specific functions such as creating an enhanced food systems data portal, and (3) *Establish* a “network of networks” to provide both global coordination as well as organize defined agendas at global through to regional scales.

In embarking on these pathways, a revised science-policy-*society* landscape (SPSIs) should deliver the following core functions: (1) Engage and empower multi-stakeholder dialogue; (2) Build capacity at multiple scales to translate evidence into tangible real-world outcomes; (3) Ensure access to openly accessible data for the entire food system; (4) Use models, forecasts, and scenario building exercises to explore the potential future of food systems; (5) Produce assessment reports and policy publications; and (6) Establish fora for diplomacy that will be empowered to create standards set targets and establish policy.

81 **1. INTRODUCTION**

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83 To achieve both the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as well as the Paris Agreement’s
84 climate change targets, food systems must support healthy diets for all and sustainable
85 production practices. But everywhere food systems are falling short. Existing food systems
86 place undue pressure on natural capital and ecosystem services while contributing significant
87 greenhouse gas emissions. At the same time, many of the world’s food systems do not result
88 in optimal dietary patterns, leading to the growing epidemic of diet-related preventable diseases
89 and undernutrition (Willett et al., 2019). Recent pandemics and armed conflicts highlight the
90 fragility of today’s food systems. To future-proof food systems while making them more
91 sustainable, the UN Food Systems Summit called for a food systems transformation that leads
92 to equitable access to affordable, healthy, and safe diets, produced in ways that are
93 environmentally-friendly and just. Such a transformation will be extremely challenging. At a
94 minimum, it will require strategies for knowledge management to inform actions, integrated
95 and coherent policy, and effective public and private sector investments (Guterres, 2021).

96
97 While there is a consensus that policies to support food systems transformations must be based
98 on the ‘best science’¹, disagreements exist on how best to link science and action (e.g., see
99 Clapp et al., 2021). Such criticisms are especially relevant given that using evidence effectively
100 often fails to deliver meaningful change. The reasons for this disconnect include insufficient
101 policy-relevant research to support consideration of alternatives, time-lags between the
102 development of policy questions and research by the scientific community, a lack of evidence
103 on ‘how’ to implement recommendations, inadequate resource allocations, and a lack of
104 capacity to interpret and deploy evidence. Obstacles also arise through decision-making
105 systems, including: i) a lack of attention to the priorities of diverse stakeholders, and especially
106 marginalized actors including small-scale farmers, women, Indigenous people and migrant
107 workers, ii) the disproportionate power exerted by large-scale producers and large food
108 processing companies and retailers, and iii) an unwillingness of policymakers to deal with
109 trade-offs, resulting in inertia as the least-difficult position to take (De Schutter, 2017 and
110 Singh et al., 2021).

111
112 Although many strong science-policy interfaces (SPIs) exist today, in general existing systems
113 that try to bridge science and policy are insufficient (von Braun et al., 2021) and better
114 integrated systems are needed to bring together fragmented advice and disparate actions across
115 current food systems (Hainzelin et al., 2021). Better policy making requires systems that foster
116 greater coherence among subject matter experts and people with lived experience on topics as
117 diverse as health, climate change, trade, social and gender equity, and biodiversity
118 conservation. There is, therefore, an urgent need for novel and more effective forms of
119 “science-policy interfaces” that extend their influence by directly including "society" to
120 become Science-Policy-*Society* Interfaces (SPSIs) (Webb et al., 2022). Recently, the European
121 Commission established a High-Level Expert Group to study this issue and make
122 recommendations. This article provides a precis of the finding of this process and discusses the
123 implications (Webb et al., 2022 is the reference to the full 70-page report that this summary
124 draws on)².

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¹ We define ‘best science’ as science that encompasses not only natural, technological and social and economic science, but also includes recognition and evidence of knowledge systems from non-traditional sources such as Indigenous cultures, citizens and private sectors.

² The full 70-page report is entitled Everyone at the Table: Transforming Food Systems by Connecting Science, Policy and Society. It is the official final report of the European Commission’s High Level Expert Group that

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2. CURRENT OBSTACLES AND CHALLENGES

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Several SPI platforms already provide both formal mechanisms and informal ways to influence food systems policy processes and functions, but each has limitations. For example, the UN’s High-Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE) reports to the Committee on World Food Security (CFS) and offers to address policy gaps. However, the HLPE does not currently have a strong enough mandate or adequate resources to lead the global charge on food systems transformation; nor does it have sufficient connections to local actors and networks to drive change at a regional or sub-national scale (see Supplementary Table 1). Separately, the Intergovernmental Panel of Experts on Climate Change (IPCC) and the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) focus on food systems’ impacts on climate change and on biodiversity loss respectively. Nevertheless, where IPCC and IPBES address food systems concerns, they mostly focus on agricultural issues and deal less (or not at all), with healthy diets and the sustainability of entire food systems. There is wide consensus, therefore, that the current SPI landscape does not sufficiently address the requirements of food systems transformation (e.g., see Fears et al., 2019).

The European Commission’s High Level Expert Group’s report on science policy interfaces reveals several key constraints that hinder the ways in which evidence translates into food systems policy. These constraints include a lack of: (1) systematic and regular forecasting, modelling, and scenario building at both global and regional levels, (2) rigorous, independent, and future-oriented assessment reports that provide indicators of the current situation along with an assessment of progress and trends, (3) input by marginalized groups (e.g. Indigenous people small-holder producers, women, and migrant labourers); and (4) a comprehensive and publicly available data portal designed to collect, store, integrate, and disaggregate data from across the food system, including data from the private sector as well as information on environmental, social and health factors (Webb et al., 2022).³

Of course, improved science policy interfaces are insufficient to enact food systems transformations. Indeed, a considerable body of food-related knowledge is currently available but has not been fully harnessed (e.g., see: Turnhout et al., 2021). Furthermore, there is a robust literature on how food systems evidence may be distorted by vested interests, and such observations highlight discourses around government intervention, legitimacy, and impacts (e.g. see Clapp, 2022). Such political concerns are also exacerbated by the fragmentation of the current landscape of SPIs that undermines our ability to systematically explore plausible futures and consider the complexity of cross-sectoral and cross-scalar processes. A more holistic approach is needed, therefore, to integrate different types of knowledge and more diverse groups of actors. Concerns are also raised that the fragmentation of the current systems leads to polarization across diverging views of how food systems should operate and be governed and that this polarization exacerbates asymmetries of power (e.g. Rotz et al., 2019). Such disagreements are exacerbated by a failure to incorporate an awareness of political

was established to assess the needs and options for strengthening science–policy interfaces for improved food systems governance. Briefly, this report explores the urgency of food systems transformations, the principles and functions needed for effective science-policy-society interfaces, reviews the landscape of current science policy interfaces for food systems, and explores pathways of transformation.

³ Some dashboards do exist, such as the Food Systems Dashboard and FAOSTAT, and these represent complementary assets around which to grow a more comprehensive system.

economy issues to address trade-offs between economic and environmental benefits, conflicts of interest, path dependencies, and conflict over whether access to adequate food is a basic human right (De Schutter, 2009).

3. PROPOSED PATHS FORWARD

In summary, the European Commission’s High Level Expert Group on Food Systems concluded that the acceptance of science and other forms of evidence into policymaking processes by state and non-state stakeholders requires continuous societal engagement (Webb et al. 2022). As such, a key goal of SPSIs should be to convene diverse stakeholders and perspectives across multiple scales (e.g., the global through to the local) and to achieve this, SPSIs must embody core principles that include political legitimacy, the participation of groups traditionally excluded from policy processes, transparency and democracy, and the ability to work across sectors and scales. To maintain these principals, the High Level Expert Group also concluded that SPSIs should aspire to provide the following functions; (1) Engage and empower multi-stakeholder dialogue; (2) Build capacity at multiple scales to translate evidence into real-world outcomes; (3) Ensure access to data for the entire food system; (4) Use models, forecasts, and scenario building exercises to explore the future of food systems; (5) Issue independent assessment reports and policy publications; and (6) Establish fora for diplomacy, standards / target-setting and policy making (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Theory of change that underpins the recommendations made by the EC’s high level expert group (adapted from Webb et al., 2022).⁴

⁴ Explanation: to drive food systems transformations, the food system must be understood from multiple perspectives (step 1). Next, the proposed functions of SPSIs (step 2) must be used to inform policy development (step 3). The light blue functions (F1-3) focus on engagement and capacity building; the light grey functions

To manifest the theory of change outlined in Figure 1, three tangible policy pathways are proposed. The first recommended pathway is for multi-lateral agencies such as the United Nations, the Rome Based Organizations (e.g. FAO) or the European Commission to *adapt* the current SPI landscape by providing extra resources and a mandate to work across the entire food system including input suppliers, producers, processors, retailers and consumers. For example, new resources and expanded mandates could be delegated to organizations such as the UN’s CFS and HLPE, the IPCC, and/or the IPBES. One (or more) of these could be tasked with working beyond traditional horizons and stakeholders by convening dialogues or other processes to engage stakeholders to achieve consensus on different topics. Another way that the existing landscape could be adapted is that the UN could work with key players in today’s landscape of SPSIs to produce rigorous assessment reports analogous to what the IPCC produces for climate change. Such reports would need to be on cross-cutting and interdisciplinary topics relevant to food systems transformations. Finally, the international community could better support data portals, including FAOSTAT and the EU-FSDN, as a way of increasing the accessibility, interoperability, and harmonization of data. In doing so, better funded data portals would also be able to establish higher standards in terms of data quality and establish global and regional hubs that would complement databases already hosted by United Nations and other organizations such as the World Bank.

A second pathway proposed by the EC’s High Level Expert Group is to *enhance* the current landscape with “multisectoral taskforces” (Webb et al. 2022). To accomplish this, multilateral institutions could consider cooperating with member states to fund smaller and agile groups with narrower mandates that would address specific knowledge and data gaps. For example, to engage different stakeholders and ensure that diverse communities, perspectives, and viewpoints are respected, a taskforce could continue facilitating the food systems dialogues that were conducted in the lead up to the UNFSS and continue the process of linking the outputs of these dialogues with regional and national pathways documents. Another task force might receive a mandate to create a blueprint for a longer-term political process that would explore what groups would be best placed to coordinate SPSIs and what kinds of institutional structure could lead to legitimate political SPSIs. A third taskforce could develop regionally relevant (and publicly available) capacity building modules to explore topics such as healthy diets, improved nutrition, etc., and embed these modules within in-country extension services.

A third proposed pathway is to *create* a “network of networks” to promote, coordinate, and drive a food systems transformation agenda. More specifically, this network of networks could ensure on-going support for integrated data portals, a higher degree of capacity building and convene regional assessments that attempt to forecast/model trends in the food system. To achieve such a series of ambitious outcomes, one strategy might be to fund a global coordination hub to identify constraints and needs experienced by local and regional partners and generate multi-directional linkages between science, policy, and community members. Another function would be to administer competitively allocated funding to support tasks related to the functions required by SPSIs. This might include issuing calls for proposals to conduct regional assessments and to convene multi-stakeholder dialogues

(F4&5) involve analysis and assessment; the dark grey function (F6) focuses on delivering policy insights. Together, these elements comprise the theory of change developed by the EC’s High Level Expert Group

(globally or in targeted regions or scales) and create future scenarios and policy pathways. Third, this approach could fund national and regional research bodies to conduct quantitative and qualitative modelling- and foresight exercises that consider local concerns, solutions, and innovations. See Figure 2 for a heuristic depiction of how these three pathways fit together.

Figure 2. Heuristic depiction of the three pathways to develop science policy society interfaces for food systems transformations illustrated as a nested series of strategies (adapted from Webb et al., 2022).

4. PERSPECTIVES AND CONCLUSIONS

Covid-19 and the global instability caused by Russia’s invasion of Ukraine demonstrate weaknesses in today’s global food system. These crises highlight the importance of developing more sustainable, equitable, nutritious, and resilient food systems. Hence, it is vital to remember that the food systems we have today are neither eternal nor accidental. Our food production methods, value chains and consumption patterns are all shaped by economic incentives, policy levers, investment decisions, social aspirations and patterns of consumer demand. These factors can be changed, and today we have a chance to make new choices. But each of these choices must be both deliberate and carefully informed by the best available evidence and insights. When appropriate evidence is unavailable, poor decisions become inevitable, and when this happens, the status quo may become even more entrenched.

Given the massive human and planetary health problems linked with today’s food systems, policy makers must access and apply not only the best scientific evidence but also other forms

263 of knowledge to support food systems transformations. On its own, however, ensuring
1 264 information is available to policy makers through traditional “science policy interfaces” will
2 265 not be sufficient. In the future, “science-policy-*society* interfaces” must empower civil society,
3 266 the private sector, academics, and policy makers to work collaboratively to build the collective
4 267 intelligences global society needs to address real obstacles to transformative change. It is only
5 268 through such a multi-sectoral engagement strategy that we shall overcome the political and
6 269 economic barriers that confound reform.

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9 271 Finally, three key conclusions can act as a foundation on which to build the pathways described
10 272 above. First, multi-lateral governance organisations, such as the EC and UN, should fully adopt
11 273 a food systems lens in all their investments and activities. Adopting such a lens will help policy
12 274 makers better understand and consider the ways in which food producers, processors, and
13 275 consumers are linked and should empower all relevant stakeholders, diverse voices, and
14 276 geographic regions to engage in food systems transformation. Second, in adopting a food
15 277 systems lens, national governments and regional bodies should work collectively to connect
16 278 stakeholders across all scales, convene regular multi-stakeholder dialogues, anticipate trends,
17 279 set targets, and articulate policy options. Such collaborations must also be organized to debate
18 280 progress to fuel action at different levels and openly explore trade-offs. Finally, as a global
19 281 community, the current landscape of SPSIs must be strengthened to engage a wider range of
20 282 voices and work to integrate different forms of evidence and data as a way of anticipating trends
21 283 and setting both targets and standards. If we can accomplish these things, true food systems
22 284 transformation is possible.

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12 351 independent panel constituted by the European Commission's (EC) Directorate-General for
13 352 Research and Innovation to advise on the need, potential, feasibility, options and appropriate
14 353 approaches for SPIs to support food systems transformation. The views expressed in this article
15 354 represent those of authors. This manuscript is an independent exercise which addresses the
16 355 implication of the HLEG-report considering ongoing debates around these issues.
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356 **Supplementary Table 1: Summary assessment of selected global institutions and networks (adapted from Webb et al. 2022).⁵**

Existing Science-Policy Interface or mechanism	Function 1: Engage stakeholders	Function 2: Capacity Building	Function 3: Facilitate access to comprehensive farm-to-fork data	Function 4: Explore the future of food systems	Function 5: Deliver independent assessment reports	Function 6: Create forum for diplomacy
High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) of the Committee on World Food Security	Lacking legitimacy to engage with all stakeholders (CFS has this mandate)	No formal capacity building activities, but informal development through engagement with national scientists engaged in writing reports and peer-review.	Limited: highlights and draws attention to other data sources.	Extremely limited; “look into the future” is very limited, not enough, and this is not done systematically and periodically.	Every four years, HLPE is tasked by CFS to identify critical and emerging issues but lacks holistic, systemic, and comprehensive assessments.	Strong ability to foster dialogue among policy makers but currently limited ability to engage broader audiences.
Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)	Global presence. Limited ability to engage with diversity of stakeholders due to lack of resources and administrative burden.	Significant efforts to enhance capacity for data collection and analysis, policy uptake of technical assistance, etc.	FAOSTAST has little ability to disaggregate data sub-nationally. Produces little on diets, nutrition or environment; data does not include private sector sources.	Limited ability to forecast or develop models. Some “over the horizon” reports are published but are not systematic or regular.	FAO’s SOFI report moves in this direction but may (or may not) be scientifically independent.	Regularly hosts dialogue with other governance agencies (such as the EU). FAO has legitimacy and authority in this regard.

⁵ It should be noted there are multiple regional organisations that provide similar functions (e.g. European Union Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR), European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) of European Union, and Future Agriculture of Africa) for specific aspects of food systems.

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<p>Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)</p>	<p>Core activities do not include engaging stakeholders. However, their outputs have the effect of engaging policymakers directly and, indirectly, to foster dialogue across scales and geographic regions.</p>	<p>Limited formal but strong informal capacity development through engagement with national scientists in high level processes, focused on data quality assessment and interpretation.</p>	<p>No capacity to do this, especially regarding food systems.</p>	<p>This is one of the core activities.</p>	<p>Produces regular assessment reports. Their remit is not about food systems, although climate change touches on food systems in several ways.</p>	<p>Assessments, briefs for policy makers, and special reports generate dialogue and attract public interest. No focus on food system sustainability directly.</p>
<p>Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)</p>	<p>Like IPCC, only smaller in scope and scale of reach.</p>	<p>Building capacity as one of six objectives and is a core aspect of strengthening the SPI for biodiversity and ecosystem services.</p>	<p>No datasets but access to journal articles and report.</p>	<p>A workstream on strengthening SPIs for biodiversity and ecosystem services, addressing interlinkages between biodiversity, water, food and health.</p>	<p>Not much focus on food systems. Prepared under UN charter and by independent scientists.</p>	<p>A secretariat hosted by UNEP. It has a Multidisciplinary Expert Panel that provides advice to the Plenary on scientific and technical issues.</p>
<p>Codex Alimentarius</p>	<p>A system for defined stakeholders to insert, share and submit comments</p>	<p>Supports periodic training to strengthen technical capacity of Subcommittees</p>	<p>Sets standards for ~200 food products and has >120 guidelines and codes of</p>	<p>The Strategic Plan presents the mission, vision, goals, objectives and measurable</p>	<p>Annual reporting of discussions and new agreements through the work</p>	<p>A multilateral body under the UN, it works through its Commission to</p>

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	on documents; for secretariats to compile comments in an easy and efficient manner and to provide data for analysis.	and National Committees and for chairs of government committees.	practice on a range of issues linked to food safety, quality and trade.	indicators for the Codex Alimentarius.	of the Codex Alimentarius.	help member states agree on food standards and specifications, food trade concerns, health issues, etc.
EAT	No regular report but engages stakeholders from academia, private sectors, farmer organisations and policymakers	Works closely with individual governments to enhance policymakers' and young professionals' capacity to engage with science.	Very limited.	Liaise with other academic institutions and science networks for forecasting, modeling and scenario building related to food systems.	EAT worked with FOLU and with the Food System Economic Commission on separate analyses and reports.	A science-based organization that operates as a global platform for food system transformation through dialogues, engagement with policymakers and donors and promotion of research.
Global Forum on Agricultural Research and Innovation (GFAR)	Stakeholder engagement is key, promoting collective actions that link farmers, civil society and NGOs, consumers, education, finance and investment	Contributed by sharing information across its networks through events, website-based information sharing and by facilitating the creation of spaces to support	Nothing on food systems. Documents and a selection of datasets on agriculture made available by partners are accessible to all.	No formal forecasting responsibilities or ambitions. GFAR channels information and fosters interaction among its members.	Promotes knowledge sharing, dialogue and investments to build partnerships, capacities and mutual accountability at all levels of the	GFAR is a network mechanism with a secretariat hosted by FAO. It fosters dialogue with 660+ partner organisations.

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	institutions, UN Agencies, public national and international research, advisory services, private sector companies, women's groups and youth organisations.	innovation and research collaborations at various levels.			agricultural system.	
Food and Land-use Coalition (FOLU)	Engage with country stakeholders regularly but only covers key countries like China, Indonesia, India, Columbia, Ethiopia, etc.	Limited to peer-to-peer sharing of research and experience.	Very limited.	Linkage with IFPRI, PIC, EAST and IIASA (FABLE) on forecasting and scenario building on food systems-related issues.	Ad hoc. Produces influential reports; Engagement with stakeholders worldwide to food systems thinking.	More than 10 global and regional ambassadors engage with stakeholders. There is no formal dialogue between FOLU and national stakeholders, however.
Regional Strategic Analysis and Knowledge Support System (ReSAKSS)	Wide engagement with regional and country level policymakers. Limited engagement with the private sector, civil society and	Limited to engaging policymakers in dialogue about research findings.	Plays an important role in generating, collecting and sharing data, indicators and analyses related primarily to Africa and, to	Works with IFPRI on forecasting and scenario building and on monitoring and identifying trends.	Produces annual reports to monitor agricultural spending, growth and other indicators related to agricultural and rural development.	Provide supports for the African Union and national governments by engaging stakeholders through conferences,

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Existing Science-Policy Interface or mechanism	Function 1: Engage stakeholders	Function 2: Capacity Building	Function 3: Facilitate access to farm-to-fork data	Function 4: Explore the future of food systems	Function 5: Deliver independent assessment reports	Function 6: Create forum for diplomacy
High-Level Panel of Experts (HLPE) of the Committee on World Food Security	Lacking legitimacy to engage with all stakeholders (CFS has this mandate)	No formal capacity building activities, but informal development through engagement with national scientists engaged in writing reports and peer-review.	Limited: highlights and draws attention to other data sources.	Extremely limited; “look into the future” is very limited, not enough, and this is not done systematically and periodically.	Every four years, HLPE is tasked by CFS to identify critical and emerging issues but lacks holistic, systemic, and comprehensive assessments.	Strong ability to foster dialogue among policy makers but currently limited ability to engage broader audiences.
Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)	Global presence. Limited ability to engage with diversity of stakeholders due to lack of resources and administrative burden.	Significant efforts to enhance capacity for data collection and analysis, policy uptake of technical assistance, etc.	FAOSTAST has little ability to disaggregate data sub-nationally. Produces little on diets, nutrition or environment; data does not include private sector sources.	Limited ability to forecast or develop models. Some “over the horizon” reports are published but are not systematic or regular.	FAO’s SOFI report moves in this direction but may (or may not) be scientifically independent.	Regularly hosts dialogue with other governance agencies (such as the EU). FAO has legitimacy and authority in this regard.
Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)	Core activities do not include engaging stakeholders. However, their outputs have the effect of engaging	Limited formal but strong informal capacity development through engagement with national scientists	No capacity to do this, especially regarding food systems.	This is one of the core activities.	Produces regular assessment reports. Their remit is not about food systems, although climate change touches	Assessments, briefs for policy makers, and special reports generate dialogue and attract public interest. No focus

	<p>policymakers directly and, indirectly, to foster dialogue across scales and geographic regions.</p>	<p>in high level processes, focused on data quality assessment and interpretation.</p>		<p>on food systems in several ways.</p>	<p>on food system sustainability directly.</p>
<p>Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES)</p>	<p>Like IPCC, only smaller in scope and scale of reach.</p>	<p>Building capacity as one of six objectives and is a core aspect of strengthening the SPI for biodiversity and ecosystem services.</p>	<p>No datasets but access to journal articles and report.</p>	<p>A workstream on strengthening SPIs for biodiversity and ecosystem services, addressing interlinkages between biodiversity, water, food and health.</p>	<p>Not much focus on food systems. Prepared under UN charter and by independent scientists.</p> <p>A secretariat hosted by UNEP. It has a Multidisciplinary Expert Panel that provides advice to the Plenary on scientific and technical issues.</p>
<p>Codex Alimentarius</p>	<p>A system for defined stakeholders to insert, share and submit comments on documents; for secretariats to compile comments in an easy and efficient manner and to provide data for analysis.</p>	<p>Supports periodic training to strengthen technical capacity of Subcommittees and National Committees and for chairs of government committees.</p>	<p>Sets standards for ~200 food products and has >120 guidelines and codes of practice on a range of issues linked to food safety, quality and trade.</p>	<p>The Strategic Plan presents the mission, vision, goals, objectives and measurable indicators for the Codex Alimentarius.</p>	<p>Annual reporting of discussions and new agreements through the work of the Codex Alimentarius.</p> <p>A multilateral body under the UN, it works through its Commission to help member states agree on food standards and specifications, food trade concerns, health issues, etc.</p>

<p>EAT</p>	<p>No regular report but engages stakeholders from academia, private sectors, farmer organisations and policymakers</p>	<p>Works closely with individual governments to enhance policymakers' and young professionals' capacity to engage with science.</p>	<p>Very limited.</p>	<p>Liaise with other academic institutions and science networks for forecasting, modeling and scenario building related to food systems.</p>	<p>EAT worked with FOLU and with the Food System Economic Commission on separate analyses and reports.</p>	<p>A science-based organization that operates as a global platform for food system transformation through dialogues, engagement with policymakers and donors and promotion of research.</p>
<p>Global Forum on Agricultural Research and Innovation (GFAR)</p>	<p>Stakeholder engagement is key, promoting collective actions that link farmers, civil society and NGOs, consumers, education, finance and investment institutions, UN Agencies, public national and international research, advisory services, private sector companies, women's groups</p>	<p>Contributed by sharing information across its networks through events, website-based information sharing and by facilitating the creation of spaces to support innovation and research collaborations at various levels.</p>	<p>Nothing on food systems. Documents and a selection of datasets on agriculture made available by partners are accessible to all.</p>	<p>No formal forecasting responsibilities or ambitions. GFAR channels information and fosters interaction among its members.</p>	<p>Promotes knowledge sharing, dialogue and investments to build partnerships, capacities and mutual accountability at all levels of the agricultural system.</p>	<p>GFAR is a network mechanism with a secretariat hosted by FAO. It fosters dialogue with 660+ partner organisations.</p>

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